

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES IN FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING COMPETITIVE PERSONNEL

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Annotation: In the process of training competitive personnel, future biology teachers are given information on the content of pedagogical conditions in the formation of professional competences.

Аннотация: В процессе подготовки конкурентоспособных кадров будущим учителям биологии предоставляется информация о содержании педагогических условий формирования профессиональных компетенций.

Keywords: cadre, competence, creativity, reflection, pedagogical culture, dictionary, methodical guide, daily, textbook.

Ключевые слова: кадры, компетентность, креативность, рефлексия, педагогическая культура, словарь, методическое пособие, дневник, учебник.

The main indicator of professional-pedagogical competence in the process of training lies in the fact that the person, the person, is oriented. Pedagogical competence covers the qualification of being able to consistently perceive and act in pedagogical reality. This feature provides an opportunity to see in the integrity of the pedagogical process logic and in combination with the whole structure, to understand the laws and directions of the development of the pedagogical system, to facilitate the construction of purposeful activities. The competence is due to the possession of modern pedagogical technologies, which are associated with three situations that are extremely important for the teacher:

- interacting with people, engaging in cultural communication;
- be able to receive information in the field of Science and use it in processing and independent study in accordance with the content of teaching;
- ability to give educational information to others.

Creativeness is the desire and skill to create a new pedagogical reality at the level of a professional way of life, a multifaceted educational process and the goals of the system, Content, Technologies. Creativity helps the teacher to adapt to the flow of innovation changes.

Professional knowledge at any level is capable of pedagogical reflex. Reflection is a special way of thinking, a re-examination of pedagogical reality, historical and

pedagogical experience, a personality that is the bearer of a certain professional position.

All the components that make up the above pedagogical competence, form a complex structure, form an "ideal model" of a specialist, and as a result, densely merge, as well as determine the description of the personal activity of the teacher.

Competence is manifested and evaluated only in the process of activity, within the framework of a concrete profession. When assessing the activities of a teacher in a pedagogical environment, usually the term "pedagogical culture" is used. Pedagogical culture is associated with the individual content of professional activity. Pedagogical competence ensures that the educator achieves high results.

In the process of education, upbringing and knowledge are formed. Knowledge is a generalized experience of people overgrown in the process of social historical practice. Knowledge is the most correct and perfect knowledge that accurately reflects the state of being, which in turn changes not only permanently, but also in the process of social progress.

On the basis of knowledge, the cognitive abilities of educators, such as observability, contemplation, memory, develop in them, religion are formed, the system of ideas that form the scientific worldview is composed.

In the formation of professional competence, it is also required for the teacher to have an idea of the forms and types of educational literature.

Educational literature - a certain type of Education (direction or Specialty) a complex of necessary knowledge is presented on the basis of relevant educational programs in the subjects mentioned in the curriculum, the methods of mastering and didactics are covered (including foreign translations) and prepared in two forms:

- traditional (printed) educational literature is a source that is printed on paper taking into account the age and psychophysiological characteristics of the educators, the size of the data, the fonts, the quality of the paper, the type of cover and other indicators;
- e-learning literature is a resource with the ability to aggregate, describe, update, Store, present and control information in an interactive way on the basis of modern information technologies.

Types of educational literature.

In the educational process of continuous education system, the following types of educational literature are used: textbook, instruction manual, dictionary,

Explanatory Dictionary, data set, lecturing course, lecturing collection, methodical instructions, methodical manuals, data bank, daily, review, etc.

The textbook is a publication established on the basis of state educational standards, methodologies and didactic requirements of the educational program, integrated into the idea of national independence, fully illuminated the topics of a particular subject, aimed at perfect mastering of the basics of the relevant science, and taking into account the possibilities of use in the directions of peer education.

He or she will have their own textbooks that cover the goals and objectives of this type of education, take into account the age and other characteristics of the cognitive person. In addition to theoretical knowledge, the textbook provides the necessary readings on practical-experimental and test exercises.

The textbook is a publication that partially complements the textbook, structured on a particular science program and provides a deep understanding of the basics of Science, with a broad coverage of some chapters and chapters, or a practical exercise and training solution.

In the educational manual, certain topics are covered more broadly than in the textbook. For example, on the subject "methodology of teaching biology", a textbook for solving questions and exercises, non-standard assignments, assessments, etc.

Dictionary collection of words (or combinations of words, idioms, etc.) that are located in a certain order, a publication that provides information about their meaning, use, origin, translation into another language, or the concept of a word, the predicate with which it is determined.

Explanatory Dictionary publication that interprets the contents of words, gives a grammatical, etymological and stylistic description of each word, examples of their application and other information, is used as an additional literature.

The data set is a publication consisting of information that is necessary to master a particular science or direction of Education, created in a convenient form for use, does not require proof, scientific indicators and dimensions, various characters and figures, short information in scientific, socio-political, practical, economic, cultural and other fields. Samples of solving a number of important scientific and practical issues should be presented in the data collection. For example, a data set based on creative approaches for future biology teachers.

Lecturing course-the main content of all subjects in the curriculum of the science is briefly covered, the primary focus is on acquiring new knowledge, the main

and additional educational literature used is shown, the series of self-control questions, the publication with the relevant base terms and phrases on the subject, the name of the lecturing course is called the name

Set of lectures - the main content of the topics in the syllabus of a particular subject is briefly covered, the primary focus is on obtaining new knowledge, the main and additional educational literature used is indicated, the series of questions on self-control, the base terms and phrases related to the subject are listed, periodic a small number of disseminated materials, which are updated.

Methodical (methodical) instruction - a small number of course works (projects) on the curriculum of a particular subject, the procedure for laboratory and practical work is clearly and in detail expressed, and is intended to create the necessary practical skills for students in this subject, published on the recommendation of the scientific (pedagogical) Council of educational institutions.

The methodical manual is intended for teachers (professors and teachers) and knowledge recipients, in which recommendations about the purpose of one lesson, the means of passing the lesson and the methods of their use, the content of the lesson, practical exercises, assignments of sheep pants, etc. are published on the recommendation of the scientific (pedagogical) Council of the institutions of education.

Commentary is a publication that interprets normative and legal documents, as well as controversial works, ideas, opinions and descriptions, which are important for the development of society, indicating solutions to certain issues, used as additional literature intended for the general public.

Daily-scientific, scientific-methodical, educational, periodical, literature, decisions of laws related to the activities of the government and various organizations, a brief description and interpretation of the contents of the regulations, a permanent publication used as a collection of information on the fields.

Electronic textbook-is intended for the application of a learning style based on computer technology, independent education, as well as effective assimilation of scientific materials, scientific information in all respects: - Educational and scientific materials only in verbal (text) form;

-educational materials in verbal (text) and two-dimensional graphic form; - multimedia (multi-informative) manuals, that is, information in the form of three-dimensional graphics, sound, video, animation and partly in the form of verbal (text);

- tactile (perceptible, perceptible) particularity is expressed in a form that creates the illusion that the O will enter the real world where the stereo copy is depicted in the "screen world" and move in relation to the objects in it.

The data bank is a collection of data on the areas recorded in the relevant authorized state organization, created on the basis of the capabilities and tools of Information Technology, structured static and Dynamic mode, provided with sound and color images, containing a large amount of information and capable of giving them in different ways (table, diagram, histogram, text, picture, etc.), applied by the

The nature of the relationship between the individual and society also dictates the connection of any social activity with self-education. Self-promotion is an important task of all labor communities, the institutionalization of which is a constant desire of life, while people is accustomed to fulfill this requirement.

The higher the effectiveness of the educational process depends on the academic potential of the teacher, his reputation before the youth, his personal qualities, scientific talent, experience and skills in the field of education, as well as his friendly attitude to students or students.

The modern requirements are dictated by the fact that professors and teachers need to diligently study the experience of foreign countries, strung their kernels, and then give lessons to their students, not limited to the knowledge and level available to them.

The effect of pedagogical activity is also dependent on the extent to which the pedagogical ability of the teacher is formed. Aptitude-refers to the process of activity that arises and develops, including the ability to know, the ability to understand, the ability to speak, the ability to get reputation, the ability to behave etc.

In the process of training competitive personnel in the global environment of today's education, the formation of pedagogical compartments of future biology teachers, the essence of the development of pedagogical competence in modern biology teachers implies its reflection of professional qualities, pedagogical competence implies not only the acquisition of special knowledge, skills by the teacher, but also the mastering of integrated knowledge, creative

Also, professional competence is always the knowledge of the specialty enrichment, study of new information, important social to be able to understand the requirements, to search for new information, to find them it is necessary to be able to process and apply at a high level in its work.

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